

1 **Homeostatic defect coupled with natural killer activation event in IBD.**

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8 We studied IBD mechanics in a small animal model *in vivo*. In the colonic mucosa, experimentally induced colitis (DSS colitis) was associated with loss of expression of the homeostasis associated metallothionein family gene *MT1* and *MT2*. Accordingly, changes in gene expression reflective of loss of homeostasis in the gut mucosa following oral DSS challenge were accompanied by silencing or repression of the natural killer receptor *CD244* and the killer cell lectin-like receptor *Klri1*. A homeostatic defect coupled with changes in natural killer activation status in the gut can be observed in inflammatory bowel disease.

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10 Citations

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